

Entomological Diversity in the Pannonian Plain: A Comparative Study of Neuroptera in Protected Sand Dune Ecosystems

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Abstract. The Pannonian Plain is large sedimentary lowlands in Central/south-eastern Europe. Two protected sand dune areas in the southern rim of the Pannonian Plain were surveyed for the presence of Neuroptera. Đurđevac sands in Croatia is a special geographical and botanical reserve, occupying only about 0.2 km², whereas Special Nature Reserve Deliblato sands in the Vojvodina province, Serbia, covers about 300 km². Among other lacewings, a few rare antlion species were observed in these reserves. The green lacewing *Chrysopa commata* was recorded for the first time in Croatia. The vegetation dynamics of the study areas was determined with a multispectral LANDSAT satellite imagery. As a result of the ecological succession (in both reserves) and afforestation (in Deliblato sands) in the past, the rate of the habitat loss and degradation processes of the sand dune ecosystems have increased to a level less suitable for the antlions assemblages.

Further key words. Antlions, nature conservation, habitat loss, Croatia, Serbia

Introduction

The Pannonian Plain is large sedimentary lowlands in Central to south-eastern Europe. Despite the high level of endangerment, a variety of natural habitats are still present in the plain, and one of the most characteristic is the Pannonian sand steppe. Sand steppes often occur in sand dune areas or so called windblown sands. The creation of windblown sands in the Pannonian Plain was linked to the erosion of large rivers, such as the Danube and Drava rivers in the past (*e.g.*, Královičová et al. 2015). In countries where at least a part of the territory belongs to the Pannonian biogeographic region, a great deal of effort

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is devoted to maintaining or restoring the natural sand steppes (Šefferoová Stanová et al. 2008).

Comprehensive studies on lacewing assemblages inhabiting Pannonian sand steppes exist only for Hungary, *i.e.*, the central part of the Pannonian Plain (*e.g.*, Gepp & Hölzel 1989; Sziráki et al. 1992; Szentkirályi et al. 2001, 2010; Szentkirályi & Kazinczy 2002; Gepp 2010). In the present study, two protected sand dune areas in the southern rim of the Pannonian Plain were surveyed for the presence of lacewings (Neuroptera).

The smaller one, Đurđevac sands (also: Djurdjevac sands; Croatian: Đurđevački pijesci, Đurđevački peski) in Croatia, occupying about 0.2 km², is a special geographical and botanical reserve (Ozimec 2016) (Figs 1–2, 6). The larger area, a Special Nature Reserve Deliblato sands (Serbian: Deliblatska peščara) in the Vojvodina province, Serbia, is a geo-morphological formation of eolian origin and covers about 300 km² (Figs 3–4, 8). Prior to the present study, only old literature records on Neuroptera for the Deliblato sands existed, with the oldest record dating back to 1863 (Pančić 1863; Frivaldszky 1877; Mocsáry 1899; Pongrácz 1914, Petrik 1958; Grozdanić & Stevanović 1969; Devetak 1996).

The aim of the study was to describe the neuropteran fauna that could be found in order to get insight into the bio-diversity of the sand dune areas near the southern border of the Pannonian Plain. Furthermore, our aim was also to get an idea of the rate of habitat loss relevant for the endangered neuropteran species.

Figures 1, 2. Đurđevac sands, Croatia. 1 – Sand dunes and grasslands are successively replaced by thicket. 2 – Grassland with dominating *Festuca vaginata* grass. Photos: DD (vi.2017)

Figures 3, 4. Deliblato sands, Serbia. 3 – Steppe. 4 – Sand dunes afforestation with *Robinia pseudo acacia* and *Pinus nigra* trees in the background. Photos: DD (vii.2016)

Material and methods

Insects were collected in the two protected sand dune areas during short visits in July 2016 (Deliblato sands, Serbia; two days) and July 2018 (Djurdjevac sands, Croatia; two days). Antlion larvae were excavated using a spoon. Adults were collected with insect

Figures 5, 6. Maps of the Đurđevac sands, Croatia. 5 – A map of the area in 19th century, The Second Military Survey (1806–1869) (Anonymus 1806). 6 – A contemporary map of the area (Google maps, <https://maps.google.com/>, 31.viii.2018).

Figures 7, 8. Maps of the Deliblato sands, Serbia. 7 – A map of the area in 18th century, The First Military Survey of the Habsburg Empire (1763–1787) (Anonymus 1763). 8 – A contemporary map of the area (Google maps, <https://maps.google.com/>, 31.viii.2018).

net and after identification returned to their natural habitat. A few voucher specimens of each species were deposited in the first author's collection. For identification, we used the keys in Badano & Pantaleoni (2014). Vegetation dynamics of the study areas was determined with a multispectral LANDSAT satellite imagery, freely available on the Earth Explorer platform (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). To evaluate the change in vegetation density, a vegetation index (NDVI) was used for each available cloud-free time window (1992–2017). Moreover, a pixel level regression tool was applied (Curve Fit) to measure the dynamics and pattern of the succession process.

Results

Neuroptera in the Đurđevac sands, Croatia

For the Đurđevac sands, there is no record in the literature of prior lacewing collection. Despite the fact that the sand dune reserve is a small area occupying only about 0.2 km², a relatively high number (17) of lacewing species was detected during the two-days of sampling (Table 1). Antlions were the most abundant and four species were collected in the sandy habitat. The most numerous antlion species was *Myrmeleon bore*, and all collected individuals were in larval stage (Fig. 9). The finding of this species was the second record for Croatia. Interestingly, the first finding place of *M. bore* in

Figure 9. Pits of *Myrmeleon bore* larvae in the Đurđevac sands, Croatia. Photo: DD (vi.2017) **Table 1.** Lacewing species recorded in 2018 in the Đurđevac sands, Croatia. Abundance: sporadic – 1–4 individuals observed; frequent – 10–49 individuals observed; very frequent – 50 individuals or more observed.

Taxon	Abundance
Chrysopidae	
<i>Chrysopa perla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	sporadic
<i>Chrysopa dorsalis</i> Burmeister, 1839	sporadic
<i>Chrysopa commata</i> Kis & Újhelyi, 1965	sporadic
<i>Chrysopa formosa</i> Brauer, 1851	sporadic
<i>Chrysopa gibeauxi</i> (Leraut, 1989)	sporadic
<i>Pseudomallada flavifrons</i> (Brauer, 1851)	sporadic
<i>Pseudomallada prasinus</i> (Burmeister, 1839)	frequent in nearby forest
<i>Pseudomallada abdominalis</i> (Brauer, 1856)	sporadic
<i>Pseudomallada ventralis</i> (Curtis, 1834)	sporadic
<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> (Stephens, 1836) s.str.	sporadic
<i>Chrysoperla agilis</i> Henry, Brooks, Duelli & Johnson, 2003	sporadic
<i>Chrysoperla lucasina</i> (Lacroix, 1912)	frequent

Hemerobiidae	
<i>Hemerobius humulinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	sporadic
Myrmeleontidae	
<i>Myrmeleon inconspicuus</i> Rambur, 1842	frequent
<i>Myrmeleon bore</i> (Tjeder, 1941)	very frequent – dominant
<i>Euroleon nostras</i> (Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785)	sporadic
<i>Creoleon plumbeus</i> (Olivier, 1811)	frequent

Croatia (Ábrahám 2008) was in the Drava river basin as well. We noted twelve green lacewing species. The green lacewing *Chrysopa commata* was recorded in Croatia for the first time.

Neuroptera in the Deliblato sands, Serbia

In contrast to the Đurđevac sands, a number of older literature records of Neuroptera exist for the Deliblato sands. In 2015, we collected 13 lacewing species, but there were a further nine species known from the literature that we did not find (Table 2). The antlion *Megistopus flavicornis* was collected in the Deliblato sands in 1988 (DD unpubl.). Similarly to the finding in the Đurđevac sands, antlions were the most abundant neuropterans also in the Deliblato sands. When old literature records were taken into account, ten species of antlions were listed altogether. Among them, three antlion species, namely *Palpares libelluloides*, *Acanthaclisis occitanica*, and *Nohoveus punctulatus*, are suspected to be extinct in Serbia due to the fact that records only older than 1983 exist.

Table 2. Lacewing species listed for the Deliblato sands, Serbia. X – Presence confirmed during this study in 2016.

Taxon	Historical reports (< 1920)	Contemporary reports (1950 >)	Collected in 2016
Chrysopidae			
<i>Chrysopa perla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		Petrik (1958)	
<i>Chrysopa formosa</i> Brauer, 1851	Frivaldszky (1877); Petrik (1958) Mocsáry (1899)		
<i>Chrysopa phyllochroma</i> Wesmael, 1841	Frivaldszky (1877); Petrik (1958) Mocsáry (1899); Pongrácz (1914)		
<i>Pseudomallada flavifrons flavifrons</i> (Brauer, 1851)			X
<i>Pseudomallada prasinus</i> (Burmeister, 1839)			X
<i>Pseudomallada abdominalis</i> (Brauer, 1856)			X
<i>Chrysoperla</i> cf. <i>carnea</i> (Stephens, 1836) s.str.			X

<i>Chrysoperla</i> cf. <i>agilis</i> Henry, Brooks, Duelli & Johnson, 2003			X
<i>Chrysoperla lucasina</i> (Lacroix, 1912)			X
<i>Chrysoperla pallida</i> Henry, Brooks, Duelli & Johnson, 2002			X
Hemerobiidae			
<i>Hemerobius humulinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758			X
<i>Symphorobius elegans</i> (Stephens, 1836)	Mocsáry (1899); Pongrácz (1914)		
Myrmeleontidae			
<i>Palpares libelluloides</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)		Devetak (1996)	
<i>Acanthaclisis occitanica</i> (Villers, 1789)	Frivaldszky (1877); Mocsáry (1899); Pongrácz (1914)		
<i>Myrmecaelurus trigrammus</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Frivaldszky (1877); Grozdanić & Mocsáry (1899)	Stevanović (1969)	X
<i>Nohoveus punctulatus</i> (Steven in Waldheim, 1822)	Frivaldszky (1877); Pongrácz (1914)	Fischer v.	
<i>Myrmeleon formicarius</i> Linnaeus, 1767		Petrik (1958); Grozdanić & Stevanović (1969)	X
<i>Myrmeleon inconspicuus</i> Rambur, 1842		Grozdanić & Stevanović (1969)	X
<i>Euroleon nostras</i> (Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785)		Grozdanić & Stevanović (1969)	X
Taxon	Historical reports (< 1920)	Contemporary reports (1950 >)	Collected in 2016
<i>Distoleon tetragrammicus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Frivaldszky (1877); Mocsáry (1899); Pongrácz (1914)		
<i>Creoleon plumbeus</i> (Olivier, 1811)	Frivaldszky (1877); Mocsáry (1899); Pongrácz (1914)	Grozdanić & Stevanović (1969)	X
<i>Megistopus flavicornis</i> (Rossi, 1790)	Pančić (1863); Mocsáry (1899); Pongrácz (1914)	DD unpubl. (1988)	

Endangerment of Neuroptera in both sand dune areas

Maps of the southern part of the Pannonian Plain depicted in the 18th and 19th century reveal that at that time sand dominated in both dune areas and they were devoid of woody plants (Anonymus 1763, 1806); cf. Figs 5, 7). Later, in the late 19th and the first half of the 20th century, intense afforestation was conducted in order to control soil erosion (for Đurđevac sands reviewed by

Petrić 2009, 2014). Consequently, former sandy areas were successively transformed into agricultural landscape or forest and only sporadic or mosaic sandy areas were left (Figs 6, 8). In both reserves, additionally, ecological succession – *i.e.*, overgrowth – occurred. The result of the ecological succession (in both reserves) and afforestation in the past (in Deliblato sands) is habitat loss.

Habitat loss is the greatest threat to antlions in both sand dune reserves. In the Deliblato sands, three antlion species have not been recorded for the last few decades (Table 2). A multispectral LANDSAT satellite imagery applied in the Deliblato sands revealed that the succession process increased to a level less suitable for the antlions assemblages. Results of the satellite imagery will be presented in a separate paper.

Discussion

Lacewings assemblages in the two sand dune areas (Deliblato sands, Đurđevac sands) in the southernmost parts of the Pannonian Plain are composed of a significantly large number of species with an antlion composition comparable to antlion assemblages in similar habitats in Hungary (*e.g.*, Szentkirályi et al. 2001, 2010; Szentkirályi & Kazinczy 2002). Sand dune reserves are important refuges for rare species, such as the rare antlion, *Myrmeleon bore*, and the typical sandy grassland inhabiting green lacewing *Chrysopa commata*. The consequence of afforestation is the occurrence of two pine-linked species, *Chrysopa dorsalis* and *Chrysopa gibeauxi*, in Đurđevac sands. At least two neuropteran species, *Acanthaclisis occitanica* and *Nohoveus punctulatus*, which were not collected during this survey and which have not been recorded in Serbia for over one hundred years (Frivaldszky 1877; Mocsáry 1899; Pongrácz 1914) are suspected to be extinct in the country.

Both sand dune areas are recognized as fragile ecosystems. The main threats to the two sand dune ecosystems in the southernmost parts of the Pannonian Plain are the ecological succession, afforestation, and disturbances such as overgrazing, animal and human treading, weed spreading, or devastating moto- and autocross. In the Deliblato sands, the rate of the habitat loss increased to a level less suitable or even unsuitable for some antlion species.

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